

1 **CHARACTERIZING HIGHLY FIBRILLATED NANOCELLULOSE BY**
2 **MODIFYING THE GEL POINT METHODOLOGY**

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12
13 **Abstract**

14 The characterization of nanocellulose fibres (NC) length is a difficult and indirect
15 measurement which relies on aspect ratio calculation and fibre diameter analysis. The aspect
16 ratio can be directly calculated from the gel point, a parameter obtained from sedimentation
17 experiments. The gel point has been used with macroscopic fibres and microfibrillated
18 cellulose, that easily sediment by gravity. However, this methodology has not yield
19 consistent results with highly charged nanofibres nor with fibres with sediment layer difficult
20 to observe. In this study, the gel point methodology is modified: 1) dying the fibres with
21 Crystal Violet to enable the visualization of the fibrils sedimentation line without affecting
22 the fibre network; and 2) by optimizing the sedimentation time to ensure complete settling.
23 The two types of fibrils characterized -low and high fibrillated NC (LF-NC, HF-NC)- behave
24 differently due to the slower sedimentation of HF-NC. The time to reach a stable sedimented
25 layer increases with the level of fibre fibrillation, the charge and the decrease of fibre
26 dimension. Reproducible gel point can be measured after 2 days for LF-NC; however, 8 days
27 are required for HF-NC. The modified methodology was validated by quantifying the
28 influence of pH and salt concentration. As expected, low pHs and the addition of CaCl₂
29 coagulate HF-NC into flocs which increase the ratio: final over initial fibres height (H_s/H_o);
30 this decreases significantly the gel point, as a lower amount of HF-NC are required to
31 interconnect all fibres. This modified method is a valuable tool for the accurate dimensional
32 characterisation of highly charged and low diameter cellulose nanofibres.

33
34 **Highlights**

- 35 • Aspect ratio of highly fibrillated nanocellulose is estimated using the gel point
36 methodology.
37 • Crystal Violet dyes nanocellulose improving the sediment visualization.
38 • Controlling sedimentation time is essential for consistent gel point measurement.
39 • Flocculation is not required to determine gel point of charged nanocellulose.

40
41 **Keywords**

42 Cellulose nanofibres; Gel point; Aspect ratio; Sedimentation; Crystal Violet.; Nanocellulose.

43 **1. Introduction**

44 Nanocellulose fibres (NC) are key materials thanks to their unique properties combining high
45 strength, stiffness, high surface area, excellent barrier properties, renewability,
46 biodegradability and low toxicity (Balea et al., 2016a; Besbes, Alila, & Boufi, 2011; Osong,
47 Norgren & Engstrand, 2016; Raj et al., 2016a; Siró & Plackett, 2010). For these reasons, NC
48 have been explored for many different applications, such as, strength additive in papermaking
49 (Ahola, Österberg, & Laine, 2008; Balea, Blanco, Monte, Merayo, & Negro, 2016b), anti-
50 microbial film (Niu, Liu, Song, Han, & Pan, 2018), food packaging (Ghaderi, Mousavi,
51 Yousefi, & Labbafi, 2014), biomedical applications (Curvello, Raguwanshi, & Garnier,
52 2019; Curvello et al., 2019; Lin & Dufresne, 2014), reinforcement for polymeric composites
53 (Saba, Paridah, Abdan, & Ibrahim, 2015; Wang & Sain, 2007) or in water treatments (Balea,
54 Monte, Fuente, Negro, & Blanco, 2017; Ma, Burger, Hsiao, & Chu, 2011). To produce NC,
55 mechanical treatments are required for defibrillation and previous pretreatments of cellulose
56 fibres, either by chemicals or enzymes, reduce energy consumption in the mechanical
57 processes and improve the degree of nanofibrillation (Blanco et al., 2018; Chauhan &
58 Chakrabarti, 2012; Khalil et al., 2014; Nasir, Hashim, Sulaiman, & Asim, 2017).

59 Several procedures have been developed to characterize NC for the most common
60 parameters, such as, morphology, fractionation, specific surface area, absorption, cellulose
61 chain length, carboxylic groups content, etc. (Blanco et al., 2018; Kangas et al., 2014; Osong,
62 Norgren & Engstrand, 2016). However, the quantification of some parameters, such as, the
63 measurement of the length of the fibres is an area in development and of high interest to
64 understand and optimize the efficiency of these products in different applications as in paper
65 reinforcement or adsorption of contaminants (Beck, Walker, & Batchelor, 2019).

66 Macroscopic fibres networks with many fibres complicate the measurement of fibres length
67 in microscope images. Therefore, aspect ratio directly allows for measuring the fibre length
68 as the diameter of fibres is easy to measure. The aspect ratio can be characterized from gel
69 point data. Gel point is a parameter calculated from sedimentation experiments. The
70 technique to measure sedimentation for oxidized cellulose nanofibres is presented in this
71 study. This data allows for gel-point, also called connectivity threshold (ϕ_g), to be calculated
72 as the volume concentration in the boundary between dilute and semi-dilute region. This
73 critical volume fraction may be considered the lowest volume fraction at which all primary
74 flocs are interconnected throughout the container, and form a self-supporting network
75 (Nasser & James, 2006; Raj et al., 2016b; Zhang, Batchelor, Varanasi, Tsuzuki, & Wang,
76 2012). Below ϕ_g concentration, the suspension does not contribute to the mechanical strength
77 of the suspension (Derakhshandeh, Kerekes, Hatzikiriakos, & Bennington, 2011).

78 The gel point was originally defined by Tiller & Khatib (1983) in their theory of sediment
79 compressible structures. However, it was not until 2001 that, Kerekes and co-workers
80 developed the gel point methodology to characterize the mobility of papermaking fibres
81 during sedimentation (Martinez et al., 2001). Afterwards, this method was adapted to
82 determine the aspect ratio of micro cellulose (MC) and NC fibres with low fibrillation

83 (Mosse, Boger, Simon, & Garnier, 2012; Varanasi, He, & Batchelor, 2013; Zhang, Batchelor,
84 Varanasi, Tsuzuki, & Wang, 2012). The aspect ratio of NC controls the processing conditions
85 and properties of sheets prepared with these materials (Varanasi, He, & Batchelor, 2013).
86 Two theories have been applied to calculate gel point; the semi-empirical Crowding
87 Number (CN) theory and the more rigorously Effective Medium Theory (EMT) (Celzard,
88 Marêché, & Payot, 2000; Kerekes & Schell, 1992; Varanasi, He, & Batchelor, 2013).
89 However, these theories present some difficulties to measure the parameters used, such as,
90 the estimation of the density of the fibres in the suspension or the behaviour of fibres when
91 they are very highly fibrillated.

92 Using the gel point as an alternative to measure aspect ratio has been effectively proven with
93 MC and lightly fibrillated NC (LF-NC) (Varanasi, He, & Batchelor, 2013; Zhang, Batchelor,
94 Varanasi, Tsuzuki, & Wang, 2012). However, the measurement of gel point based on
95 sedimentation curves with highly fibrillated nanocellulose (HF-NC) are more complicated
96 according to Raj et al (2016b), due to the slow sedimentation, the difficulties in visually
97 observing the sediment and the different behaviour compared with LF-NC. They used salts
98 to compress the electric double layer and screen the electrostatic repulsion between fibres,
99 thus destabilizing the fibrous system and altering the nanofibre network. Therefore, new
100 alternatives are still required.

101 The gel point has been used with macroscopic fibres and MC that easily sediment by gravity,
102 but not with nanofibrillar systems such as those in this study (Varanasi, He, & Batchelor,
103 2013; Zhang, Batchelor, Varanasi, Tsuzuki, & Wang, 2012). This is because the
104 methodology developed for macroscopic fibres previously cannot be used with highly
105 charged fibres as Raj et al., 2016b indicates, nor can it be used for fibres where the sediment
106 layer is difficult to observe. Therefore, a new methodology was developed. The method
107 should avoid altering the NC networks while enabling visualization of NC sedimentation of
108 colloidal size.

109 NC were obtained from secondary fibres by an oxidation pretreatment, to obtain highly
110 charged fibres easier to separate by homogenization. The source of cellulose is not important
111 as the aim is simply to produce a very fibrillated product for the study. However, secondary
112 fibres were used to support the trend in recycling paper mills to produce NC from recycled
113 pulp to improve the quality of their products. In the first part of the study, the gel point
114 methodology is optimized using suspensions of TEMPO NC. In the second part, the results
115 achieved are validated by investigating the effects of pH and salts addition. Last, the
116 behaviour of two different NC suspensions (HF-NC and LF-NC hydrogels) is compared. It
117 is our objective to further the application of the gel point sedimentation technique to charged
118 colloidal suspensions of high aspect ratio independently of their source and treatment.

119 **2. Experimental**

120 **2.1. NC preparation**

121 NC were obtained from 100% recycled old newspaper (ONP) with 14% ash content,
122 manufactured by Holmen Paper Madrid (Madrid, Spain) and prepared with two types of

123 treatments to obtain two suspensions: HF-NC and LF-NC, as shown in Figure 1. First, ONP
124 was left to soak in tap water 24 hours to encourage the swelling of fibres. Then, it was
125 disintegrated by using a PTI pulp disintegrator (Vorchdorf, Austria) at 30,000 revolutions
126 and 3.0 wt. % consistency, according to ISO 5263-1 standard.

127 HF-NC were obtained using a common chemical pretreatment, NaClO/NaBr/2,2,6,6-
128 tetramethylpiperidin-1-oxyl-radical (TEMPO) at 25°C and pH 10 (TEMPO-mediated
129 oxidation) according to Saito, Kimura, Nishiyama, & Isogai (2007) with 10 mmol of NaClO
130 per gram of dry pulp. The TEMPO-mediated oxidation of cellulose selectively, oxidizes the
131 C6 primary hydroxyls of cellulose to a C6 carboxylic groups which facilitates the fibrillation
132 of the cellulose due to repulsive forces. Once the pulp was oxidized, a filtration cleaning
133 process with a plastic mesh was performed using distilled water until the pH was 7 to remove
134 all the reaction medium reagents until a final consistency around 10 wt.% of fibres. Finally,
135 cellulose nanofibrillation was achieved with four steps of homogenization at 600 bars in a
136 laboratory homogenizer PANDA PLUS 2000 manufactured by GEA Niro Soavi (Parma,
137 Italy).

138 LF-NC were obtained by refining the pulp in a PFI mill, a laboratory fibre mechanical refiner
139 ~~scale refiner used to beat pulp fibres~~ manufactured by Hamjern Maskin AS (Hamar, Norway)
140 for 5,000 revolutions. Once the pulp was refined, it was diluted to 1.0 wt. % consistency and
141 six steps of homogenization at 600 bars were applied in the mentioned laboratory
142 homogenizer.

143

144

Figure 1. HF-NC and LF-NC preparation

145 Both HF-NC and LF-NC suspensions were stored at low concentration (~1 wt. %) to
146 minimize their aggregation. They were refrigerated at 4 °C, after adding a few drops of

147 glutaraldehyde bactericide (5 drops/L) to prevent the bacterial growth, until they were used.
148 Finally, HF-NC and LF-NC were characterized (Balea et al. 2016a).

149 **2.2. Characterization of NC**

150 Nanofibrillation yield degree was determined by centrifugation of 0.1% of dry NC
151 suspension at $4500 \times g$ for 30 min. The nanofibrillated fraction was isolated in the
152 supernatant, and the yield was calculated as the fraction of dry solids in the supernatant to
153 the total dry solids (Gonzalez et al., 2014).

154 The carboxylic groups of oxidized fibres were determined by conductimetric titration before
155 homogenization. A pulp sample containing 0.15 g of dry NC was added to 5 mL of 0.01M
156 NaCl, and deionized water was added to a total volume of 55 mL. pH was adjusted to 2.5-
157 2.8 by adding 0.1M HCl to protonate carboxylate groups. The samples were characterized
158 on a Crison GLP32 conductivity meter (Crison, Barcelona, Spain), 0.05M NaOH was added
159 to the sample in 0.1 mL increments and conductivity values were recorded after each
160 addition. Curve of conductivity vs. NaOH (meq) added was used to calculate carboxylic
161 groups according to the method described by Habibi, Chanzy, & Vignon in 2006.

162 To determine the charge of NC suspension, the cationic demand was calculated based on the
163 colloidal titration of 0.1 % wt. NC suspensions with 0.001 N Polydiallyldimethylammonium
164 chloride (polyDADMAC) on a Müttek PCD04 particle charge detector (BTG Instruments
165 GmbH, Herrsching, Germany).

166 The polymerization degree (PD) was calculated from the limiting viscosity number of the
167 NC suspension, which was determined by the ISO 5351 standard (2010) according to
168 Equation (1), where η is the intrinsic viscosity (mL/g), K and a have different values
169 according to PD. When $PD < 950$, $K = 0.42$ mL/g and $a = 1$, when $PD > 950$, $K = 2.28$ mL/g and
170 $a = 0.76$ (Balea et al., 2016a; Henriksson, Berglund, Isaksson, Lindström, & Nishino, 2008).

$$171 \quad \eta = K \cdot PD^a \quad (1)$$

172 Transmittance readings of 0.1% wt. CMF suspensions diluted were performed in the range
173 between 800 nm and 400 nm on a Cary 50 Conc UV-visible spectrophotometer using distilled
174 water as reference (Varian Australia PTY LTD, Victoria, Australia).

175 Finally, NC were characterized by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) with a JEM
176 1400 microscope (JEOL, Tokyo, Japan). The microscopic analyses were carried out in the
177 National Centre of Electronic Microscopy at the Universidad Complutense de Madrid. To
178 prepare the samples, some drops of diluted suspensions (0.01 wt. %) were dried on a copper
179 grid covered with a carbon coat. Image J software was used as image processing program
180 and diameter distribution of the suspensions were evaluated by measuring in different images
181 the diameter of the fibres.

182

183 **2.3. Gel point determination**

184 Gel point was evaluated according to the sedimentation methodology converted by Martínez
185 et al. (2001). A sample of 250 mL of HF-NC or LF-NC with several concentrations is used
186 in all cases. To facilitate the visualization of the nanofibre sedimentation, 1.5 mL of Crystal
187 Violet dye 0.1 wt. % is added to the HF-NC sample to dye the nanofibres (Drnovsek &
188 Perdih, 2005). For LF-NC the dye is not necessary as shown in Figure 2. Thus, control
189 experiments with LF-NC were carried out to ensure the dye did not affect the network
190 behaviour of the fibres at the concentration used for gel point.

191 Suspensions were stirred with a high-speed overhead stirrer Heidolph RZR 2051 (Heidolph
192 Instruments, Schwabach, Germany) at 50 rpm for 10 minutes and added into graduated
193 cylinders. The suspensions were settled for several days to fully allow the fibres to settle;
194 sedimentation heights were measured with time to draw sedimentation curves. Then, the final
195 height of fibres was registered (H_s) and compared with the initial height (H_o), for that, the
196 relation (H_s/H_o) was used.

197

198 **Figure 2.** Sedimentation experiments: after 48 hours:

199 a) LF-NC without dye; b) HF-NC with dye.

200 To develop gel point values, a graph of initial solid concentrations (ϕ_o) versus the ratio of
201 sediment height to initial suspension height (H_s/H_o) was plotted and fitted with a quadratic
202 equation without independent term in which a is the coefficient of second-degree and b the
203 coefficient of first-degree (Equation 2). The linear term of the fit or the initial slope of this
204 relationship (b) gives the gel point value as Equation 3 shows (Martinez et al., 2001; Mosse,
205 Boger, Simon, & Garnier, 2012; Tiller & Khatib, 1984).

206
$$\phi_o = a \left(\frac{Hs}{Ho}\right)^2 + b \left(\frac{Hs}{Ho}\right) \quad (2)$$

207
$$b = \phi_g = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{d\phi_o}{d\left(\frac{Hs}{Ho}\right)} \right) \quad (3)$$

208 There are key conditions required before a gel point obtained from a fit can be considered.
209 The first is that the data set and fit must extrapolate to the origin, since by definition there
210 can be no sediment layer with a concentration of 0. The second condition is that $a \geq 0$ and
211 $b > 0$. This is because the b term reflects the compaction of the layers with increasing weight
212 of sedimented fibres above.

213 **2.4. pH and salt concentration on gel point of HF-NC**

214 To validate the method, the well-known effects of pH and salt addition on the suspension
215 behaviour was also studied (Ampulski & Neal, 1989; Nordholm, Rasmusson & Wall, 1993).
216 In brief, changes of pH and salts affect the stability of fibres which may induce coagulation.
217 The main effect of pH is to affect fibre surface charge which becomes neutral under acid
218 conditions. Salts compress the thickness of the electric double layer around the fibres. In both
219 cases, particles are destabilized which may lead to agglomeration of the fibres.

220 The electrical charge of colloidal suspensions is determined by zeta potential (ζ) (Prathapan,
221 Thapa, Garnier & Tabor, 2016). NC suspensions diluted at 0.1 wt. % was measured using a
222 Zeta Potential analyser Zeta90 Plus (Brookhaven Instruments Corp., New York, USA).

223 The suspensions were prepared in the same way previously described. pH was adjusted with
224 NaOH 0.1M or HCl 0.1M, while CaCl₂ 0.01M and 0.8M was used to control conductivity.

225

226 3. Results and discussion

227 3.1. NC production

228 Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of the HF-NC and LF-NC fibres and Figure 3 shows
229 their TEM images. The HF-NC fibres produced by TEMPO-mediated oxidation have a
230 higher content of carboxylic groups (0.81 mmol COOH/g) than LF-NC (0.07 mmol
231 COOH/g) produced only by mechanical processes, without any chemical pre-treatment. HF-
232 NC, with high content of carboxylic groups, have a lower degree of polymerization than LF-
233 NC which agrees with the shorter nanofibrils observed in the HF-NC (Figure 3ab). Moreover,
234 the presence of NaClO as oxidant in TEMPO-mediated oxidation bleached the pulp and
235 reduced the amount of lignin (Ma et al, 2012). Additionally, these new charged carboxylic
236 groups produce repulsive forces that facilitate the defibrillation of cellulose during the
237 mechanical process obtaining a higher nanofibrillation yield (nanofibrillation yield degree of
238 HF-NC were 80% compared to 39% in LF-NC). This means that almost all the solid material
239 was effectively nanosized (Besbes, Alila & Boufi, 2011; Saito, Kimura, Nishiyama & Isogai,
240 2007). The cationic demand represents the anionic nature of the fibres and it has been
241 traditionally used to determine the extent of fibre delamination of beaten papermaking pulps.
242 High cationic demand is expected for HF-NC due to both oxidation and large fibrillation.
243 Figure 3cd shows the TEM images of the LF-NC produced only by mechanical processes.
244 Several images were taken at different resolutions to analyze the thickness of LF-NC. As
245 Figure 4 indicates, the diameter ranges of NC follow a log-normal distribution. HF-NC fibre
246 diameters were between 5 and 80 nm with a geometric mean of 15 nm of diameter. On the
247 contrary, LF-NC have a higher diameter range with some fibre diameters higher than 1 μm
248 and a geometric mean around 47 nm. Some of the nanofibres are not elemental because they
249 contain several elemental fibrils. The analysis of the images shows nanofibres networks that
250 intertwine among themselves. Therefore, the length of the fibres is difficult to know and
251 aspect ratio is required to obtain the length of the nanofibres.

252 **Table 1.** Characterization of HF-NC and LF-NC.

Parameter	Units	HF-NC	LF-NC
Concentration	(% by weight)	1.03±0.01	1.08±0.01
Nanofibrillation degree	(%)	78.4±3.4	39±5
Carboxylic Groups	(mmol COOH/g)	0.81±0.10	0.07±0.10
Cationic Demand	(meq/g)	0.62±0.02	0.044±0.003
Polymerization Degree	(monomeric units)	201±5	703±4
Transmittance 400 nm	(%)	15.4±0.4	1.8±0.4
Transmittance 800 nm	(%)	35.7±0.5	8.7±1.4

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**The grid observed in the Figure 3a is due to the carbon coat.*

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Figure 3. TEM images of: a-b) HF-NC; c-d) LF-NC.

261

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Figure 4. Fibres diameter distribution: a) HF-NC; b) LF-NC.

3.2. Effect of time sedimentation in gel point

The variation of fibre sizes shows a different behaviour between LF-NC and HF-NC fibres. Therefore, before gel point determination, the sedimentation curves of the NC are required at different concentrations to evaluate when the deposit formed is constant. Figure 5 represent the different behaviour of LF-NC and HF-NC fibres in sedimentation. LF-NC relative heights decreases with time (Figure 5a). This line separates the clear liquid from the constant sedimentation zone. These zones are easy to differentiate thanks to the dye adsorbing on the nanocellulose. However, at the beginning, the interphase between the sedimentation zone and the sediment produced is not visible. With time, sedimentation curves tend to stabilize and show the amount of sediment formed. As the sedimentation curves are constant after 2 days, the experimentation does not require more time. For concentration effect, a higher LF-NC concentration increases the H_s/H_o , as expected, but also increases the time required for a constant sediment. This is because the physical interactions between fibres prevent sedimentation which controls suspension stability (Chaturvedi et al., 2018; Kumagai et al., 2019).

HF-NC behaviour is quite different, as shown in Figure 5b. HF-NC at concentrations higher than 1 g/L behaves as LF-NC. However, a lower concentration of HF-NC have a different behaviour. Initially, the dilute suspensions are colloidally stable and a clear liquid zone cannot be seen. After a certain time, sedimentation is observed as a small deposited layer in the base of the cylinder. The sediment size first increases, and then is slightly compacted. By comparing both NC samples, we notice that the smaller HF-NC fibres sediment slower. Whereas gel point can be measured when the sediment height is constant after 1 day for conventional wood fibres (Martinez et al., 2001) or 2 days (Raj, Varanasi, Batchelor, & Garnier, 2015; Raj et al., 2016b; Varanasi, He, & Batchelor, 2013) for LF-NC, the HF-NC fibres require more time to reach a stable sediment. Although after 3 days the sediment seems to be stable, a detailed study reveals that the optimum time to reach reproducible data is indeed 8 days, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Sedimentation curves: a) LF-NC; b) HF-NC.

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294

295 Figure 6 show initial concentration of NC vs. H_s/H_0 , for different sedimentation times. This
 296 is to emphasise the time difference in sedimentation and thus determine the time required to
 297 obtain the gel point. The linear parameter of the quadratic fit of the curve gives the calculated
 298 gel point and is shown in the tables appended. For LF-NC (Figure 6a), at low sedimentation
 299 times, the curves are reversed. From 12 hours, the curves upwardly concave and gel point is
 300 almost stable from 1 day. Therefore, 2 days are enough to determine the gel point. In the case
 301 of HF-NC (Figure 6b), at low sedimentation times and for concentrations under 1 g/L, the
 302 curves show the anomalous behaviour described previously as they do not go through the
 303 origin. This effect disappears after 1 day. This trend is in accordance with Raj et al., 2016b
 304 reporting NC without salt aggregation to follow such behaviour. After 8 days, the curve to
 305 determine gel point levels off and is quite similar to the curve achieved after 1 month. The
 306 shape of these graphics is also upwardly concave and pass through the origin, just as observed
 307 with MC and LF-NC (Raj et al., 2016b; Varanasi, He, & Batchelor, 2013). There is little
 308 change in the calculated gel-point when increasing the sedimentation time from 8 days to 1
 309 month. A period of 8 days was thus selected as best time period to measure the equilibrium
 310 gel point. The results show that the time required to reach a stable sedimented layer depends
 311 on the sample type; thus, it must be optimized for each new sample.

312 Here, it must be emphasized that colloids do not tend to sediment easily. This is disturbing
 313 as equilibrium sedimentation is required for the gel method. The smaller the size, therefore
 314 the higher the interfacial area, and the higher the surface charge, the more stable is the
 315 suspension. In our study, NC fibres, while of colloidal size and much smaller than the original
 316 fibres, have a higher density ($\sim 1.5 \text{ kg/m}^3$) as more crystalline. This contributes to increase
 317 the settling velocity. However, the NC zeta potential of -30mV to -38mV , depending on pH,
 318 is high. Colloids of zeta potential higher than 30mV are usually considered stable (Honary
 319 & Zahir, 2013). The fact that the suspension still sediments, but after a long period of 1 to 8
 320 days, is very likely due to the high aspect ratio of the colloids. Driven by Brownian motion,
 321 the fibres diffuse and rotate while in suspension. This generates collisions, leading to fibre
 322 entanglement, flocculation and subsequently sedimentation.

323

Time	Gel point (g/L)
30 min	Not calculable
2 h	Not calculable
12 h	2.224
1 day	1.960
2 days	1.876
7 days	1.905

Time	Gel point (g/L)
15 min	Not calculable
2 h	Not calculable
1 day	3.042
2 day	3.462
8 days	3.703
1 month	3.747

324

325

Figure 6. Initial concentration of NC vs. Hs/Ho to determine gel point.

326

a) LF-NC; b) HF-NC.

327

328 As described by Varanasi, He, & Batchelor (2013), EMT and CN theories are used to obtain
 329 aspect ratio and the length of NC fibres from gel point value and using two densities of NC
 330 (1300 and 1500 g/m³) (Table 2). Fibres density is difficult to determine because the dry fibres
 331 are hydrated in the suspension and therefore, have a higher effective density between the
 332 density of dry fibres and water (Varanasi, He, & Batchelor, 2013). ~~As shown in~~ From TEM
 333 images in which the average diameter is obtained and the aspect ratio calculated from EMT
 334 and CN theories, the length of fibres using both theories is shown in Table 2 (Raj et al.,
 335 2016b). Both theories and densities indicate a similar average length for each type of fibre.
 336 A light fibrillation with mechanical pre-treatment (LF-NC) produce larger fibres while a
 337 higher fibrillation with chemical treatment such as TEMPO oxidation (HF-NC) reduces both
 338 diameter and length due to the intensive forces of defibrillation.

339 **Table 2.** Aspect ratio and length of LF-NC and HF-NC according to CN and EMT theories.

ρ (kg/m ³)	O_g (wt.%)	Aspect ratio CN	Aspect ratio EMT	Length CN (μm)	Length EMT (μm)
LF-NC ($\text{O}_g = 1.88$ g/L; Average diameter = 46.6 nm)					
1300	0.00244	113	101	5.26	4.70
1500	0.00282	112	101	5.23	4.69
HF-NC ($\text{O}_g = 3.70$ g/L; Average diameter = 15.1 nm)					
1300	0.00481	80.3	68.8	1.21	1.04
1500	0.00555	79.9	68.6	1.20	1.04

340

341 **3.3. Influence of pH and salt concentration on gel point of HF-NC**

342 To validate the methodology adaptation to nanocellulose fibres, the effect of pH and salt
 343 concentration was studied with HF-NC using crystal violet as dye and 8 days settling. pH
 344 above the COO⁻ pKa (4.8) increases charge and suspension stability, while increasing the
 345 concentration of multivalent salt compresses electrical double layer and reduces stability,
 346 respectively (Mendoza et al., 2018). The more stable the suspension and the longer it takes
 347 to sediment. Figure 7 compares the curves initial concentration versus height relation at five
 348 pH values: 3, 5, 7.5, 10 and 12. The curves were fitted, and gel point is shown in the linear
 349 parameter. Pre-treatment with TEMPO-mediated oxidation increase the number of carboxyl
 350 groups on the NC fibres and produce a negative primary charge in NC aqueous suspension,
 351 which creates repulsive forces that prevent their agglomeration (Bratby, 2006; Suopajarvi,
 352 2015). However, adjusting pH to 3 reduces the fibre charge, achieving the isoelectric point
 353 as zeta potential indicates, and produces destabilization of the NC suspensions and
 354 aggregation of the fibrils. Fall, Lindström, Sundman, Ödberg, & Wågberg (2011) developed
 355 a semiquantitative model that estimates pH effect on NC suspensions and indicate that when
 356 the pH is reduced, the concentration of protons close to the NC fibril surface are further
 357 increased because of electrostatic attraction. This leads to the protonation of carboxyl groups
 358 and a reduction in the surface charge that induces fibril aggregation. In our case, the NC
 359 aggregation at pH 3 produce the formation of flocs that increases the Hs/Ho ratio and
 360 decreases significantly the gel point. Then, close to neutrality, the pH curves (pH 5, 7.5, 10)
 361 show very little difference between them with similar zeta potential values. The presence of
 362 low amounts of H⁺ or OH⁻ does not affect carboxyl groups obtained by TEMPO mediated
 363 oxidation in COO⁻ groups and electrostatic repulsion between fibrils is maintained. However,
 364 higher pH values such as pH 12 produce more repulsion forces between carboxyl groups
 365 which increases Hs/Ho, especially at high concentrations. This is in accordance with Zhang,
 366 Batchelor, Varanasi, Tsuzuki, & Wang (2012) that tested NC that were similarly
 367 mechanically treated (LF-NC) and reported the same trend after two days settling. The
 368 aggregation of NC at pH 3 has the lowest gel point as expected, due to the NC aggregation
 369 producing a total connection of primary flocs at lower concentrations. When pH increases

370 under the isoelectric point, NC agglomeration are avoided, and gel point values increases
 371 considerably (Blanco, Negro & Tijero, 2001; Mendoza et al., 2018; Pelton, 1993). Increasing
 372 pH to 5, barely produces a decrease in gel point, which indicates a slight improvement in the
 373 connection between fibres and lower HF-NC concentrations required to obtain a totally
 374 connected fibres network.

375

376 **Figure 7.** HF-NC concentration vs. Heights relation for different pH values.

377 The production of HF-NC require the chemical oxidation of the fibres catalysed with TEMPO
 378 to improve fibrillation, and NC charge after oxidation is 14 times the cationic demand of LF-
 379 NC (Table 1). This increase in charge produce an electro-repulsion effect of the surface
 380 charges that slows down the sedimentation of fibres. Raj et al. (2016b) studied the effect of
 381 HF-NC (CNF from VTT refined and homogenized but without a chemical treatment) and the
 382 curve solids concentration vs. Hs/Ho reported did not go through the origin. This is associated
 383 to the charges of HF-NC that decrease the sedimentation speed; longer sedimentation time is
 384 required to measure the gel point. Figure 8 shows the differences of HF-NC with and without
 385 salt addition. Experiment without CaCl₂ after 2 hours have similar trend as reported by Raj
 386 et al. (2016b) without salt after 2 day. The curve fitting is imprecise and the curves do not go
 387 through the origin. However, when HF-NC are settled for 8 days, the behaviour becomes
 388 similar to LF-NC, with a curve that passes through the origin. Therefore, in spite of salt
 389 addition, longer settling periods are proposed to measure and calculate a stable gel point.

390 The experiments with salt were performed with three CaCl₂ dosages: 0.1, 5 and 30 mmol/g
 391 of HF-NC. The Hs/Ho ratio was measured after 8 days. A low electrolyte concentration of
 392 0.1 mmol CaCl₂/g HF-NC increases slightly the ratio Hs/Ho at all fibre concentration.
 393 However, higher doses of CaCl₂ produce an aggregation of fibres because of the higher
 394 content of carboxyl groups and the increase of Hs/Ho with a decrease of gel point. High
 395 electrolyte concentrations decrease or suppress the thickness of the electrical double layers
 396 of the NC which induce fibres aggregation into flocs in the aqueous solution.

397 The effect is similar to that produced at low pH (Fall, Lindström, Sundman, Ödberg, &
 398 Wågberg, 2011; Liu et al., 2019; Wen, Wei, Cheng, An, & Ni, 2017). Fukuzumi, Tanaka,
 399 Saito, & Isogai (2014) also studied the effect of adding salts in solutions of LF-NC prepared
 400 with TEMPO-mediated oxidation. For CaCl₂, the NC started to aggregate from concentration
 401 of 0.4mM. 4mM CaCl₂ solution is required to aggregate all NC fibrils in suspension.

402 In our study, 5mM of CaCl₂ was added to HF-NC suspensions differing in concentrations to
 403 develop the curve in which all HF-NC aggregates. This is achieved as zeta potential increases
 404 towards neutrality. A higher addition of salt, such as, the experiments with 30 mmol/g of
 405 CaCl₂ (all the experiments with more than 5 mM of salt), present a fitted curve with similar
 406 results than 5 mM curve. This fact indicates all HF-NC are already aggregated and higher
 407 dosages of salt maintain gel point. On the other hand, the experiments with 5 mmol CaCl₂/g
 408 NC have only a fraction of HF-NC aggregated. Therefore, Hs/Ho ratios are in the middle
 409 between aggregated and non-aggregated NC. Finally, the gel point obtained with the addition
 410 of CaCl₂ decreases in comparison with HF-NC suspensions without salts. This is due to the
 411 aggregation of fibres and the mechanism are identical to that at low pH values.

412

413 **Figure 8.** HF-NC concentration vs. Heights relation for different CaCl₂ concentrations.

414 **4. Conclusion**

415 The gel point is a sedimentation methodology traditionally used to characterize the average
416 dimensions of macroscopic fibre suspensions by measuring their sedimentation profiles. This
417 technique has never been used for high aspect colloidal systems or highly charged fibrillated
418 suspensions. The scaling down in cellulose fibres size from the micro to the meso and nano
419 scale requires the adaptation of the methodology to characterize charged TEMPO
420 nanocellulose fibres. Two improvements are required. Firstly, enabling visualization of the
421 sedimentation line of fibrils of colloidal dimensions. Secondly, optimizing equilibrium
422 sedimentation by neutralization of charge and increasing settling time. The methodology
423 was optimized using highly fibrillated TEMPO nanocellulose (HF-NC). The two
424 improvements developed consist of:

- 425 a. Using Crystal Violet to dye HF-NC fibres, improving the visualization of nanofibres
426 sedimentation experiments.
- 427 b. Developing sedimentation curves to assess the time required to obtain persistent
428 deposits. This equilibrium time increases with the level of fibre fibrillation and the
429 decrease of fibre dimension. This optimization is essential to determinate a gel point
430 without the influence of time.

431 The modified gel point methodology was validated by studying the influence of pH and salt
432 concentration. As expected, low pH values and the addition of CaCl_2 produce the
433 agglomeration of HF-NC forming flocs that increase the H_s/H_o ratio. In these cases,
434 flocculation induces the gel point to decrease as a lower amount of HF-NC are required to
435 interconnect all fibres.

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443

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